

FROM POLICY TO PRACTICE: EVALUATING THE 2022 ENGLISH CURRICULUM REFORM IN ALGERIAN PRIMARY SCHOOLS: PARENTS' PERSPECTIVES FROM RELIZANE*

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Abstract

This study examines the implementation of Algeria's 2022 English curriculum reform in primary schools, drawing on "language policy from below" (Menken & García, 2010) and focusing on parents as active agents in the reform. It assesses parents' attitudes toward early English instruction, their perceptions of simultaneous English-French learning, implementation challenges, use of private tutoring, and equity concerns. A convergent mixed-methods design was employed. Quantitative data were collected from 113 parents in Relizane, Algeria, and supported by written interviews with seven primary school English teachers. The study finds that while 98 % of parents support English instruction, 61 % believe learning English and French simultaneously is burdensome. The most frequently reported challenges were English-French interference (62 %), insufficient instructional hours (44 %), large class sizes (25 %), and lack of teaching materials (23%). Private tutoring was used by 34.5 % of families, driven by insufficient school hours, learning difficulties, pursuit of academic success, and poor teacher qualifications, with monthly costs ranging from less than 1000 DZD to 3000 DZD. Moreover, 69 % of parents believe private tutoring worsens educational inequality. Teacher interviews confirmed these challenges. The study concludes that the 2022 reform faces implementation gaps; without addressing curriculum overload and material shortages, the reform risks widening educational inequality. This study provides the first empirical data on parents' perspectives from Relizane and offers insights for post-colonial contexts implementing early English education alongside competing colonial languages.

Key words: Algeria, Early foreign language learning, Educational equity, English curriculum reform, Private tutoring.

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1. Introduction

In an era marked by the acceleration of globalization, English has become more than a mere language; its position as a *lingua franca* impacts educational policies in non-English-speaking countries (Alam, 2023). Political authorities tend to shape the country's educational system, including curriculum design, in order to maintain national cohesion and assert sovereignty (Tollefson & Pérez-Milans, 2018), as is the case in post-colonial Algeria. Since its independence in 1962, the Algerian educational system has gone through a series of reforms; more recently, decision makers made several attempts to deal with the effects of French colonialism, which lasted more than a century, by adding English to the national curriculum to strike a balance among linguistic identity, economic competitiveness, and educational equity (Lahmer, 2024).

It is worth noting that the Algerian linguistic landscape is a complex entanglement of Algerian Arabic (Darja), Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), Tamazight (Berber), French, and increasingly English (Benrabah, 2014; Lahmer, 2024). While French retained significant importance for a long time, especially in education, administration, and the professional world, its long prevalence as a colonial heritage has been a subject of public debate for decades (Lahmer, 2024). Calls for change have grown louder, particularly during the 2019 *Hirak*, advocating for radical reconstruction of Algeria's linguistic hierarchy (Maraf & Vanci Osam, 2023). As pressure increased and in response to public calls for change, the Algerian government implemented a reform mandating English as a required subject in primary schools from the third grade starting 2022-2023 (Lahmer, 2024). The Algerian President Abdelmadjid Tebboune announced this decision, marking a sharp break from earlier policies that had positioned English as a secondary foreign language taught in middle school (Lahmer, 2024). Two sets of arguments were used to publicly defend the reform: first, the immediate alignment of the reform with the theoretical benefits of early exposure to foreign languages such as metalinguistic awareness and cognitive development; second, the positioning of English as an alternative to French which is historically deep-rooted and broadly spoken and has long served as a language of science and global business—a role that English holds today (Hichour, 2025). Thus, the 2022 English reform is best understood not as a simple curricular change, but as a strategic policy intervention shaping the country's future language use.

Despite the ambitious policy goals the reform may carry, translating its objectives into effective classroom practice has always been a challenge, as successful implementation depends on various degrees of infrastructure development, teacher training, and resources. Recent studies on the subject highlight substantial gaps between the rhetoric of reform and the realities of implementation. Immediate challenges include issues related to teachers' qualifications and the availability of pre-service and in-service training, differentials in access to material resources, and the addition of another subject into an already overloaded curriculum (Lahmer, 2024); Additionally, there is concern that insufficient public provision could inadvertently promote the development of a private tutoring market, thereby deepening existing inequities in educational access and restricting the reach of the reform to students from more socio-economically advantaged backgrounds (Lahmer, 2024).

This research does not focus on official policy documents but rather on the families who are the core of the reform. The research will examine parents' position regarding the new English reform at the primary level; their concerns about simultaneously learning two foreign languages (English and French), the hardships their children endure in their public schools, whether they are using private tutoring as a solution for assistance, and their views on educational inequities due to private tutoring. By amplifying parents' voices, this article provides a ground-level perspective on the 2022 reform that has been absent from existing research. Although this study focuses on curriculum overload, private tutoring, and educational inequality in Relizane, its findings may have implications for other countries, especially in post-colonial contexts that introduce English into primary education, where other colonial languages compete with English.

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What are parents' attitudes toward the 2022 English curriculum reform, and to what extent do they support early English instruction?
2. What implementation challenges do parents observe in public school English instruction, including concerns about simultaneous English-French learning?
3. To what extent does private tutoring mediate the reform's implementation?
4. Do parents perceive it as a source of educational inequality?

2. Literature Review

Traditional language policy focuses on formal formulations: government decisions regarding laws, curricula, and official announcements, aiming to institutionalize certain languages, restrict others, or preserve specific languages (Nandi, Kasares, & Manterola, 2024). This top-down approach often neglects grassroots actors. In contrast, "language policy from below" is a bottom-up approach in which parents, teachers, and community members act as de facto policymakers (Menken & García, 2010; Plüddemann, 2013). This implies that if a government introduces a new language into schools, parents' responses (whether support, opposition, or disregard) determine whether the reform succeeds or fails. Therefore, this research employs a "language policy from below" framework focusing on parents as active agents in educational change.

2.1. Previous Empirical Studies on Parent Attitudes

Many research studies on Algeria's 2022 English reform found that parents had a positive attitude, driven by recognition of English's global importance. While parents are highly motivated to support their children, researchers have reported several challenges: interference from French, lack of resources, and poor teacher qualifications (Hichour, 2025; Rabahi, 2024; Lahmer, 2024). Lahmer (2024) reported parents' concerns about the overload of the curriculum, which exceeds children's capacity, especially learning two foreign languages simultaneously at a very young age. According to parents, this curriculum burden neglects slow learners, forcing them to seek private classes, which disadvantages low-income families and leads to deepening social inequity.

2.2. International Perspectives

Cenoz and Jessner (2000) point out that learning two foreign languages concurrently exhausts young learners. Similarly, Fullan (2007) describes initiative

overload as the fragmented, incoherent adoption of too many, often contradictory, educational reforms at once, leading to "reform fatigue" in which teachers feel overwhelmed and resist change, eventually placing an academic burden on students. Bray and Hajar (2022) describe "shadow education" as private tutoring that imitates school curricula; however, Bray, Kwo, and Jokić (2016) show that this type of tutoring frequently exacerbates socioeconomic inequality.

2.3. Identified Gap in the Literature

Most studies did not thoroughly systematically analyse private tutoring or equity concerns. No published study has systematically examined parents' concerns about curriculum burden (English and French together), private tutoring, and equity concerns in Relizane. This study addresses these gaps by providing the first empirical data on parents' perspectives from Relizane.

3. Methodology

A convergent mixed-methods design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) was used to generate quantitative data from a parent questionnaire and qualitative data from written teacher interviews. The two tools were collected simultaneously, analysed separately, and the results were merged in the interpretation. A parent questionnaire was chosen because it enables researchers to gain a large amount of standardized, quantifiable data to reveal attitudes, concerns, and behaviour patterns and trends. In addition, questionnaires save time and money, and ensure anonymity, which may lead to more honest answers on sensitive issues such as private tutoring and equity. The parents' questionnaire was originally written in Arabic and then translated into English for analysis.

Moreover, we opted for written interviews with teachers as this tool is useful for busy teachers, allowing them to answer at their own pace, eliminating the need for transcription, translation or cleaning and providing immediate usable written data. Besides, unlike oral interviews, written ones help avoid interviewer bias and give teachers more time to think through responses (Bowden & Galindo-Gonzalez, 2015). Teacher interviews provide qualitative data and deeper perspectives to triangulate and strengthen parent findings. They consisted of eight open-ended questions covering classroom challenges, resources, training, and recommendations. Ethical approval was obtained before data collection; all participants were informed of the voluntary nature of the study and assured of their anonymity.

The study took place in Relizane city, which was selected because it is a mix of urban and semi-urban schools, offering a varied context; plus, there are no previous studies on the 2022 English reform in this region. Survey participants included parents of children enrolled in Grades 3, 4, and 5 in public primary schools in Relizane. After removing incomplete and conflicting responses, 113 parents (out of 120) completed the questionnaire, and their responses were retained for analysis. Seven primary school teachers of English were interviewed.

The parent questionnaire was written in Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), drawing from the theoretical framework of language policy from below (Menken & García, 2010). Initially, we attempted to distribute paper questionnaires through primary

schools in Relizane, but due to limited parent engagement, we shifted to an online version of the same questionnaire using Google Forms, distributed via Facebook parent groups in Relizane. Consequently, the sample is a convenience sample of digitally connected parents. Data were collected over 4 weeks (March–April 2026). The questionnaire consisted of 14 items divided into six sections. Participants were informed that the questionnaire was anonymous, participation was voluntary, and no names or contact information were collected. All participants provided digital informed consent before completing the questionnaire. All data are stored on a password-protected computer accessible only to the researcher. Questionnaire data were downloaded from Google Forms as a CSV file, then imported into Microsoft Excel for analysis. We calculated frequencies and percentages for all closed-ended items, while open-ended responses were analysed thematically. To ensure the five Likert-scale attitude items are consistent and non-contradictory, we used Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a value of 0.87, indicating good internal consistency.

Written semi-structured interviews were conducted with seven primary school English teachers. The interview protocol consisted of eight open-ended questions covering parent-teacher interactions, English-French interference, private tutoring, classroom challenges, and recommendations. Responses were analysed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Parents' Questionnaire Analysis

4.1.1. Parents' Demographics

Regarding family size, the majority of families had one child in primary school (57 %), while 28 % had two children, and 12.5 % had three or more children. 37 % of children are enrolled in third year 3PS, 29 % in fourth year in 4PS, while 31% in fifth year 5PS. Thus, the children in this study began English after the reform was already in place, reflecting the reform's ongoing implementation rather than its initial rollout. The majority of parents held university degrees (52 % of fathers, 68 % of mothers).

4.1.2. Parent Attitudes toward English

Table 1. Parents' Attitudes toward English (N=113)

Statement	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
English is important for my child's future	98 %	0 %	2 %
English will help my child get better job opportunities	94 %	2 %	4 %
English is more useful than French in today's world	88.2 %	4.5 %	7.3 %
I wish I had learned English when I was young	86 %	7 %	7 %
English complements other languages and is not a substitute	82 %	7 %	11 %
English threatens my child's Arab or Amazigh identity	18 %	11.5 %	70.5 %

These findings confirm that parents support English for its usefulness in their children's future careers, with only 18 % viewing it as a threat to their child's identity. This aligns with previous studies (Rabahi, 2024).

4.1.3. Satisfaction with English Teaching

Table 2. Parent Satisfaction with Public School English Teaching (N=113)

Level of Satisfaction	N	%
Very satisfied	28	25%
Satisfied	42	37%
Neutral	12	11%
Unsatisfied	22	19%
Very unsatisfied	9	8%
Total	113	100

While 62 % of parents are satisfied with English instruction, only 27% remain dissatisfied, indicating an implementation gap that undermines parental confidence in the reform.

4.1.4. Difficulties Observed in English Teaching

Table 3. Reported Difficulties Observed by Parents (N=113)

Difficulty / Observation	N	%
Insufficient number of hours	50	44 %
Large class size	28	25 %
Lack of books / teaching materials	26	23 %
Inadequate teacher training	10	9 %
No noticeable difficulties	20	17 %
Child mixes English and French	70	62 %
Learning English and French simultaneously constitutes a heavy burden on primary school children	69	61 %
Lack of administration follow-up	4	3.5 %
Too many lessons / curriculum overload	3	2.5 %
the curriculum focuses on aural skill primarily, writing skill isn't emphasized	3	2.5 %

Note: Parents could select multiple options or add their own responses. Percentages do not sum to 100 % because multiple responses were allowed.

The most reported difficulty was English-French interference (62 %); this was reinforced by a similar majority 61 % who agreed that learning both languages simultaneously constitutes a heavy burden. These findings support Cenoz and Jessner's (2000) claim that learning two foreign languages concurrently fatigues young learners. Insufficient hours (44 %) and large classes (25 %) reflect systemic hindrances.

4.1.5. Private Tutoring and Educational Inequality

Table 4. Receipt of English Learning Support (N=113)

Does your child receive English learning support?	Number of parents	Percentage
Yes	57	50.4 %
No	56	49.6 %
Total	113	100 %

Note: Support includes both paid private tutoring and free assistance. 57 parents (50.4 %) reported that their child receives English learning support, while 56 parents (49.6 %) do not.

Table 5. English Learning Support Providers (n=57)

Provider	N	%
Mother	18	32 %
University student	11	19 %
Teacher from same school	3	5 %
Teacher from another school	7	12 %
Private language centre	11	19 %
Online teacher (WhatsApp, Zoom)	7	12 %

Among the 57 parents who reported supporting their children's English learning with multiple free and paid sources, mothers are the most common free source (32 %) suggesting parental support is very common; while the remaining parents pay for the lessons from different providers. 39 parents seeking paid tutoring represent 34.5 % of the total 113 parents, which is a significant percentage.

Table 6. Monthly Cost of Private English Tutoring (N=39)

Amount (DZD)	Count	Percentage
Less than 1000 DZD	19	49 %
1000 – 3000 DZD	17	43.5 %
3000– 6000 DZD	2	05 %
More than 6000 DZD	1	02.5 %
Total	39	100 %

Table 7. Reasons for Seeking Private English Tutoring (N=53)

Reason	N	%
School hours are insufficient	25	47 %
My child was struggling with English	10	19 %
I want my child to be ahead of classmates	10	19 %
English teacher at school is not well qualified	8	15 %

Note: Parents could select multiple reasons, so N=53 represents total responses, not the number of parents.

Table 8. Parent Perceptions of Educational Inequality (N=113)

Statement	Agree (%)
Children who cannot afford private tutoring are in an unequal position	62 %
Wealthy children will become better at English than poor children due to tutoring	69 %

Insufficient school hours, children struggling with English, desire for academic advantage, and poor teacher qualifications are the main reasons that drive parents to seek private tutoring. The findings suggest that 39 of 113 parents (34.5 %) pay for private lessons; 51.3 % pay less than 1000 DZD monthly, while 43.5 % pay between 1000 and 3000 DZD. The findings suggest that 34.5 % of parents paying for private lessons is a relatively significant number, indicating private English tutoring is in increasing demand due to the above-mentioned reasons. If unaddressed, the parallel tutoring market could expand and threaten educational equity. Moreover, a great majority of parents are concerned that private tutoring creates educational inequality, believing that wealthy children will outperform economically disadvantaged children.

4.1.6. Suggestions for Improvement

Table 9. Parent Suggestions for Improving English Teaching (N=113)

Suggestions	Percentage
Reduce class size	39 %
Increase number of English hours	37 %
Provide better teaching materials (books, audio, videos)	36 %
Improve teacher training	24 %
Provide free support classes at school	18.5 %
Do not teach two foreign languages together	2.5 %

Note: Parents could select multiple options, so percentages do not sum to 100 %.

The top three parent recommendations were reducing class size (39 %), increasing English hours (37 %), and providing better teaching materials (36 %). These recommendations directly address the reported difficulties.

4.1.7. Parent Comments and Emerging Themes

Beyond the quantitative data, parents' open-ended responses revealed additional themes that were not explicitly covered in the closed-ended questions. Most parents expressed happiness and gratitude for the reform. *“Introducing English at primary school is one of the best decisions, my kids are very happy. Thanks to the subject teachers as they made a difference in public schools.”*

The above-mentioned comment strongly proves the parents' linguistic orientation toward English and acknowledges the teachers' efforts. Nevertheless, the

great majority expressed dissatisfaction with teaching English and French concurrently, rejecting French outright and calling for delaying or eliminating it, as it creates learning overload and pronunciation confusion.

“Two languages at the same time have exhausted our children, in addition to the Arabic curriculum. Our children have become guinea pigs”.
“In French, children write in cursive. In English, children write in script. This is an additional burden for a Year 3 child who already has problems with Arabic expression and even with multiplication tables. In regions where Tamazight is taught, tell me about it! Three languages at the same time!”

This comment provides deeper insights into the 3PS curriculum, revealing the curriculum overload that forces children to acquire a set of languages written and spoken differently when they are initially learning their own mother language and struggling with foundational skills; in addition to switching between two writing systems (cursive for French, script for English). Policymakers also overlooked the cognitive load of learning four languages in 4PS (Arabic, Berber, French, and English).

Several parents expressed empathy for teachers' working conditions, recognizing that overloaded teachers cannot deliver quality instruction. One parent noted:

“English teachers in primary school are exhausted by the large number of classes and students across two or more schools. How can you expect positive results from a teacher who is mobile and overloaded with nearly half a school's students?”

As observed, parents recognized that teachers' well-being matters, as teacher burnout directly affects their children's learning. Parents aren't attributing the issues to teachers but the system, which overworks them and expects fruitful results. Moreover, some have suggested reducing pressure on teachers by hiring more teachers, and reducing the assigned classes and levels:

“I suggest adding more teachers; it's unfair for a teacher to teach multiple classes in more than one school. Delivering courses will be tiresome, and teaching will be ineffective”. “No more than 3 groups per English teacher and 2 levels at most.”

Parents also called for updating the program to align with global teaching frameworks. One respondent specifically recommended adopting British Council programs, creating mobile applications and providing effective teacher training, emphasizing that successful learning does not stop when a student steps out of school, but remains motivating and continuous outside.

“We must ensure proper and good training for language teachers, as well as follow well-known global programs such as 'Global English' from the

British Council, as they have an excellent, comprehensive, and useful curriculum. Also, create special applications for the school and the curriculum to motivate students to study even outside official school hours."

Some even feel nostalgic for the old system as it matches learners' different abilities. They believe the current one is dense, focuses only on quick learners, and neglects slower ones; they recommended revising it, implying that as long as the situation remains the same, there will always be a weakness. One parent, a teacher of English herself, declared that the English program focuses primarily on speaking and neglects writing, resulting in significant weakness in writing skills. One parent simply requested a workbook; this simple yet essential learning material is crucial because it focuses on practicing writing letters, words, and sentences.

4.2. Teacher Interview Analysis

To triangulate and deepen the findings from the parent questionnaire, written interviews were conducted with seven primary school English teachers in Relizane. Their responses provide critical perspectives on implementation challenges, curriculum appropriateness, English-French interference, and private tutoring.

4.2.1. Background Information

The seven teachers had an average of 3.5 years of teaching experience. Most taught across two to four different schools, with class sizes ranging from 27 to 40 students, which are relatively large classes. This mobility across multiple schools and large class sizes was a recurring theme throughout the interviews.

4.2.2. Thematic Analysis of Teacher Responses

Theme 1: Parental Support of the Current Reform

The majority of teachers reported that parents are positive and supportive of English instruction. T1 noted that parents are "*excited as their children*" while T3, T5, and T6 described them as "*happy and satisfied*". T2 and T4 stated that they are supportive, while T7 said: "*even though some parents are quite supportive of the decision since English is the international language, some others feel worried to teach both English and French at the same time*". Teachers' reports indicate parents' positive attitudes towards the reform, though some raise concerns.

Theme 2: English-French interference Concerns

Almost all teachers confirmed the parents' concerns about English-French interference. They demonstrated that this issue is real and persistent, providing concrete examples: learners mix alphabets, numbers, colours, days of the week and words with similar spelling, notably at 3PS. They attributed this pattern to the simultaneous introduction of both languages at this level and called for delaying the introduction of French.

"Yes, pupils often confuse English with French because they are learning both languages at the same time. For example, when learning the days of the week, some pupils say Lundi instead of Monday or Mardi instead of Tuesday," one teacher elaborated.

This remarkable alignment between parent concerns and teacher observations suggests that English-French interference is not a mere perception but a lived reality policymakers should address.

Theme 3: Private Tutoring Demand

Five teachers out of seven reported that parents regularly request private tutoring highlighting five main reasons: (1) to help their children acquire the language; (2) to help their children improve and keep up; (3) the number of hours dedicated to English is too short for them to learn effectively, (4) the big number of learners does not allow the teacher to pay attention to each learner, they fear their children will be left behind. Hence, they opted for private tutoring; (5) Parents want tutoring to ensure high grades.

Regarding whether tutored learners perform better in English, five teachers affirmed that they observed remarkable progress and attributed this enhanced performance to extra practice, as two weekly hours are insufficient. T1 offered a different view, arguing that if they revise at home or a family member helps them, they will be good at English, suggesting that even home support alone can be the determining factor. Another teacher argued that, due to the large number of learners in class, limited time and the teacher being tied up by the yearly distribution, there is little room to follow each learner; some parents fear their children being left behind, so they opt for private tutoring. T7 provides a concrete example of a student who was really bad at English. However, after attending private classes for less than a month, she could see observable progress, especially in their vocabulary.

These findings align perfectly with the parents' survey; the reasons cited by teachers match the parent survey data almost exactly: parents request tutoring because the two weekly hours are insufficient, and overcrowded classrooms prevent individual attention. The findings also suggest that the key factor is extra practice, not private tutoring in itself.

Theme 4: Teachers Face Significant Classroom Challenges

When asked about challenges in teaching young learners, teachers reported two categories of challenges: systemic issues and developmental challenges. The systemic issues are related to the educational system itself, including scarce resources, insufficient training, limited instructional time, teaching large classes and the heavy burden of teaching across multiple schools.

Regarding the availability of teaching materials (textbooks, audio materials, flashcards, projectors, posters, etc.), five teachers said that textbooks are available, but they still need workbooks and other materials that are not provided by the school, so they had to buy them with their own money. Most teachers struggle with the poor infrastructure for the reform, noting that parents also declared the absence of the same materials:

“There is no projector, and audio materials are not provided. As a result, teachers often have to search for audios”.

“The lack of materials needed has pushed the teachers to buy materials using their own money which burdened them economically”.

Teacher training is a key factor in the success of the reform, as it is supposed to prepare teachers for classroom realities. When asked about the training they received, three teachers said it was beneficial; one of them praised the British Council online training, whereas four teachers stated it was too short, basic and did not adequately prepare teachers for the realities of the primary classroom. They noticed insufficient training on managing interactions and implementing effective strategies for managing behaviours and preventing disruptions. This suggests that the current training model is flawed. Hence, some areas of teachers' training programs need improvement: they should be extended in duration, include more practical classroom management strategies, and provide specialized modules for teaching young learners.

Beyond these systemic issues, teachers also face developmental challenges that are related to the characteristics of young learners themselves, such as short attention spans, high energy, disruptive behaviour, and varying ability levels, which make the class hard to manage. T7 stated that *“Teaching English to young learners aged 8–9 can be challenging because their attention span is short, which makes it difficult to keep them focused throughout the lesson. In addition, the large number of pupils in each class limits individual participation and makes classroom management harder”*. These developmental traits do not exist exclusively within an Algerian context but rather are universal features of young learners. However, when combined with large class sizes and limited time, managing students becomes more difficult, hindering the teaching process.

These findings suggest that ensuring reform success does not hinge solely on curriculum design but also requires addressing developmental realities and systemic constraints. By providing efficient training, smaller classes, more instructional time, and reducing teacher mobility across schools, teachers can manage the natural developmental challenges of young learners.

Theme 5: Teachers' Recommendations and Overall Assessment of the Reform

When asked what aspects they would change about English teaching in primary schools, teachers suggested a set of recommendations that closely matched those of parents.

Table 10. Teachers' Recommendations Compared to Parent Demands

Teacher Recommendation	Number of Teachers	Corresponding Parent Demand
Increase English hours	4	37% of parents wanted more hours
Reduce class size	4	39% of parents wanted smaller classes
More specialized teacher training	3	24% of parents wanted better training
Improve teaching materials	3	36% of parents wanted better materials
Focus on writing	2	mentioned in parents' comments

However, the most reflective response came from T7, who concluded:

“Well, I do think that the 2022 English reform is a positive step, but it was introduced rather very quickly without enough preparation for teachers or even schools. Many schools still lack materials and resources, which makes implementation difficult. More training and support are needed to ensure the reform is effective”.

This comment captures the reform perfectly: while the policy goal is widely welcomed, it is deficient in its rushed implementation, under-resourcing, and flawed teacher training.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the 2022 English curriculum reform from the perspectives of 113 parents and seven teachers in Relizane. The findings reveal an implementation gap: despite the wide support for English, systemic challenges burden both teachers and learners. A weak infrastructure (characterized by a lack of basic materials and inadequate teacher training) stems from hasty implementation. The simultaneous teaching of English and French in 3PS has created language confusion compounded by different writing systems. The curriculum overload worsened the situation by a hidden burden of four languages (Arabic, Berber, French and English). Insufficient instructional hours, large class sizes, and the program’s failure to accommodate individual differences (leaving slower learners behind) have pushed many families toward private tutoring, fearing their children will be left behind. Unfortunately, some parents believe that wealthier children will outperform poorer children because of access to private tutoring, which threatens the reform's equity goals. Teachers working across multiple schools are exhausted, affecting instructional quality.

Teacher interviews confirmed and extended the survey’s findings and implementation gaps: insufficient training and scarce resources force them to buy materials with their own money; teacher burnout results from poor teaching conditions.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to policymakers, parents and teacher training institutions to address the implementation gap and improve the 2022 English curriculum reform.

Policymakers should reconsider the program and balance the four skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking. They should also consider delaying French instruction until Grade 4 or 5 to mitigate language interference and curriculum overload, increase English instructional hours and add support sessions, which would help slow learners. It is strongly encouraged to reduce class sizes and to provide teaching materials such as workbooks, posters, tablets, audio materials, and projectors to allow for individual attention, particularly for slow learners. Finally, it is advisable to improve teachers’ well-being by stabilizing them in a single school, which may reduce their pressure on them.

Parents in this study expressed strong concerns about curriculum overload, large classes, poor infrastructure, and simultaneous English and French learning. Parent

associations may wish to raise these concerns with policymakers, including the possibility of delaying French instruction. Private tutoring is a means to personal excellence, not an end in itself. Parental support and follow-up can be effective since most English learning support providers are mothers; many parents already support their children at home. Parents are encouraged to assist their children's writing through extra practice and simple remedial work at home. Mothers who successfully help their children could share practical strategies on social media or at parent meetings, such as revision techniques, useful online resources, books, and time management tips. This may reduce reliance on paid tutoring and enhance parent-to-parent support.

Teacher training institutions should extend the current training period and focus more on practical, in-class experience rather than theory since teachers reported being unprepared for classroom management, young learner psychology, and individual differences. Institutions should also consider adding specialized modules addressing young learners' psychology, individual differences, and class management. Training programs should offer strategies for managing young learners and minimizing disruption, not just English teaching methods. Finally, programs should focus more on practical teaching rather than theory.

7. Limitations

While conducting this study, we encountered several limitations. First, the study is limited to Relizane; the results may not be applicable to other wilayas. Besides, because it was distributed online, parents without access to the internet, Facebook, or other technology may have been excluded. The sample over-represents university-educated parents (52% of fathers, 68% of mothers), which limits generalizability to all parents in Relizane. Some parents didn't answer all the questionnaire items, especially open-ended questions. Some teachers provided brief or incomplete interview responses, limiting the depth of the qualitative analysis.

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